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Department of Software Development and Entrepreneurship

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Author

Abraham Sylvester

DIGITAL INVISIBLE INK WRITING: IMPERCEPTIBILITY & SECURITY ENHANCEMENT TECHNIQUE

Steganography “focus on LSB and AES 256Bits”

Supervisor

Anton Vedeshin

Lecturer

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Abbreviations

LSB Least Significant Bit

MSB Most Significant Bit

RGB Red Green Blue

SB Secret Byte

HC Hiding Capacity Histogram

HVS Human Vision System

AES Advanced Encryption Standard

DES Data Encryption Standard

IDEA International Data Encryption Algorithm

BSC Bit Stream Cipher

SSIM Structural Similarity Metrics

SHA Secure Hash Algorithm

PNSR Peak Signal Noise Ratio.

(MSE) Mean Square Error

Abstract

In this era of accelerated change of overwhelming complexity and tremendous competition with the ever increase of malicious attacks, adversaries of different types continue to pose a challenge on private sector and government documents in the cyber world and as far as the world of technology that we live is concerned, I strongly think that security should not just be perceived as a slogan but as a way of life. Because there is no amount of security that can ever be perfect, but just enough security to keep both our tangible and intangible assets up and running. Otherwise, the internet would remain a play zone for hackers. The HackersNews Media has reported that financial institutions are increasingly dealing with unauthorized data exfiltration attempts in which a bad actor smuggles data like credit card numbers out past the organization's detection systems or by passing the radial by masking the information in unremarkable files. Even to this day, steganography is still practiced. Recent news posted from TheHackersNews portal also mentioned that: Hackers of ecommerce website have now devised new approach for concealing stolen credit card information within an image - no doubt, this is another form of steganography).

Steganography has been in practice since the ancient times. The authors refined the meaning of the craft and science of apparent communication which is also referred to as the art of digital invisible ink communication. This implies that hiding of information from raising a suspicion can be achieved by concealing secret message behind objects e.g. images or picture's so as to dissuade an intruder's attention from the stego image, during a communication session. As stated by (Morkel et al., 2005), hiding of information is not sufficient, in other guarantee information confidentiality, integrity and availability, it is very important to conceal the existence of the secret message by using steganography.. The objects can be any of the following: image, audio or video. Steganography is but a termed that is extracted from the Greek words "stegos" meaning "cover" and "grafia" meaning "writing" and by combining both words, we now attain what is called "covered writing". However, when we talk about image steganography the information hidden is limited to images. I think that steganography is the digital art of invisible writing ever invented by man. That can be used to conceal the existence of secret message.

Cryptography only tends to conceal or transform the original payload of a secret message from readable format or plain text into ciphertext or unreadable format. On the other hand, steganography focuses more on hiding the very existence of a secret message. Ever since, steganography has been sought after in different ways. Even spies adopted the use of invisible ink writing. Also by Da Vinci when he hides a secret meaning in a painting that is steganography. It is no doubt that this concept is greatly in use in today's digital world, where a file like an image of various extensions such as: .jpg, .jpeg .png, .gif, etc. provides the possibility to implement stealth information encoding. Steganography involves a series of processes to hide a message within an object. In order to ensure that the hidden message will not be apparent to a third party. And I strongly think that security should not just be perceived as a slogan but as a way of life as far as the world of technology that we live is concerned.

This paper explores steganography from its earliest instances, problems of steganography techniques, analyse image files formats for steganographic content, potential future application, security and payload or image perceptibility enhancement techniques. In addition, a demonstration of brute force attack was implemented on the stego image, in order to test the robustness of the developed system. It was also observed that some of the best file formats which are considered to be more suitable for steganography are those with a high degree of verbosity or redundancy. In this scenario, redundancy is termed as the amount of bits streams or data can be skipped without affecting the actual significance and purpose of information.

Keywords: Steganography, Cryptography, Steganalysis, Stego image, payload, imperceptibility and Least significant bit (LSB)

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Over time, cyber security defenders and digital forensics specialists have focused more on this area, employing advanced and sophisticated techniques to intercept encrypted files and combine them with metadata – allowing them to track down communication targets and criminals. Cyber thieves and extremists, on the other hand, are also aware of this development. The big question is how to distinguish between an image that has been altered for legitimate reasons and one that has been altered to hide malicious information. Information concealment is insufficient, and as a result, cybercrime will continue to grow in popularity because it is so profitable. Steganography has the potential to worsen the problem. The field of steganography has attracted so much interest in the last decades. A good steganographic technique should not only base on concealing or enciphering of data but should make more emphasis on the following: Integrity, hiding capacity, quality of the cover image and robustness(Rabie et al., 2018). Several methods and techniques have been explored and proposed to guarantee data security and protect privacy. Encryption happens to be probably the most obvious in use, and then emerges steganography. A comparison between encryption and steganography ist that encryption in of itself tends to easily draw attention which can easily be observed or spotted but on the other steganography may not be observable or easily detected(Cheddar & Sc, 2009).

Steganography is the conventional application of concealing sensitive or private information into an "guilt-free" cover medium, generating a "stego" medium. The cover and the stego mediums should be indistinguishable and inconspicuous to eavesdroppers(Rabie et al., 2018). On April 08, 2017, according to Dark Reading portal, over the years, the field of data security has gained more awareness due to increase of illicit access to confidential information also known as cyber espionage. According to Kaspersky Lab, it was noted that three cyber warfare efforts and many ransomware elucidated in recent months have used steganographic techniques. Which is prominently predicting the potential the alarming trend in the field of data security which has undoubtedly motivated information technology analysts and developers to pursue technological solutions to secure the privacy of documents sent over communication networks(Rashid et al., 2017) and also possible ways to enhance security methodologies. Although the practice of steganography was used in ancient centuries, this technique is busily used today by different cyber perpetrators.

Steganography is defined as the very art and science of concealing the fact that communication is being established. Steganographic systems can hide or conceal messages also known as payload inside of images or other digital objects. To a casual observer inspecting these images, the messages are invisible(Amirtharajan et al., 2010). It is more important to ensure the safety of your data than to hide it(Faleh, 2014). Cryptography is often used to protect information secrecy through making messages illegible(Li et al., 2011). As a matter of concern, It is not only sufficient to encrypt the contents of a payload; it may even be important to hide the message's presence. An approach that can be used to achieve this is referred to as steganography. As the field of science or technology would define it,

Steganography is termed as the art of invisible communication(Morkel T. et al 2006). Cryptography is often used to protect information secrecy through making messages illegible(Li et al., 2011).

Researchers try to develop steganography schemes that complicate the process of the detection, and to a lesser extent the extraction, of the hidden data. The endeavours from researchers largely focus on security improvement. However, reaccessing this critically, security is not the exclusive aspect open for improvement. Other critical aspects that need to be addressed includes: stego quality, hiding capacity, and robustness of the stego system(Rabie et al., 2018). The advancement of cryptography or encryption technique is drastically on the move apropos ensuing endless possibilities. Stenography is the technique of concealing information through veritable files. It's derived from a Greek word meaning "covered writing"(Padmavathi & Kumari, 2013). LSB steganography is based on the changing of one or more of the last 1-4 bits of a cover image's pixels is imperceptible to human visual systems. The LSB technique has unlimited rooms for flexibility to offer because of its adaptability when it comes to security enhancement. i.e alot revolve around LSB technique not only because of its simplified approach but its dynamicity makes it more reliable. The application of LSB can be carefully examine within the spatial domain. It operates mainly by manipulating the(least significant bits) attributed by a cover image, which is used for hiding secret data(Cem et al., 2018). The majority of available techniques for color picture steganography have been confirmed to use chaos-based and symmetric-key based cryptographic algorithms, which are inefficient and unsuitable for large amounts of data. However, hash-based (MD5 and SHA-2 have flaws) algorithm-based approaches seem to be significantly faster in terms of time, but these approaches are poor or vulnerable in terms of protection due to inherent flaws caused by the used checksum approach(Riasat et al., 2011). The provocation to manoeuvre through these threats has prompted researchers to seek solutions that can dispense reliable security protocol for securing multimedia data by ensuring integrity and copyright protection. These services should not affect the availability and the performance of the communication system. Another technique which researchers have now developed to achieve the security goals via these communication systems is called Multimedia steganography.

1.2 Problem Statement

Researchers try to develop steganography schemes that complicate the process of the detection, and to a lesser extent the extraction, of the hidden data. The endeavours from researchers largely focus on security improvement. However, reaccessing this critically, security is not the exclusive aspect open for improvement. Other critical aspects that need to be addressed includes: stego quality, hiding capacity, and robustness of the stego system(Rabie et al., 2018). No robust approach for color image steganography is available that is not only efficient in terms of less computation workload but also provides flawless and secure data transmission(Amirtharajan et al., 2010) and (Amirtharajan et al., 2018). Concordantly, (Jassim, 2013) stated the obvious problem that most data hiding systems take advantage of human perceptual weaknesses. It is almost impossible for the human eyes to tell the difference between unaltered and altered steganographic image. I think that the imperceptibility

weakness has been one of the challenging dilemmas as far as the field of steganography is concerned. Agreeably, (Cem et al., 2018) stated that the goals of image steganography mainly boils down to the three(3) following factors: imperceptibility, capability(capacity), and security or robustness.

Articulating to the paper by (Setiadi & Jumanto, 2018) went further to explain that the existing techniques, typically used for color image steganography, use various symmetric-key cryptographic algorithms such as AES, DES, and IDEA. However, these algorithms are slow and unsuitable for large data sets. Other algorithms, such as BSC, MD5, and SHA, are inefficient when it comes to delivering flawless security. Because of these issues with existing methods, the field of steganography has remained unpopular and ineffective. The Least Significant Bits(LSB) method is considered to be a very simple approach, as a result this makes it very predictable and vulnerable to attacks. Although, researchers are still investigating this technique in order to improve it drawbacks(image quality and safety) says (Setiadi & Jumanto, 2018). This is due to LSB's benefits in imperceptibility quality, which means that small changes are not detected by the human vision system. “As a result, in order to increase the accuracy, secret message, and robustness of message insertion, LSB is integrated with a variety of approaches, including insertion in edge regions, cryptographic techniques, adaptive and dynamic LSB” (Setiadi & Jumanto, 2018).

Digital photographs have a high level of representational redundancy and are commonly used in daily life, making them appealing for data concealment. As a result, over the last decade, there has been a surge of interest in image steganography and image steganalysis (Li et al., 2011). According to (Rabie et al., 2018) The relationship between the hiding capacity and stego quality is typically characterized by a trade-off that researchers try to overcome. The quality of the stego medium is usually lowered when large quantities of data are hidden in the cover medium, and vice versa. As a result of this negative impact on quality, hiding capacities have remained relatively low. Despite the fact that many researchers have tried a variety of methods with little success. Despite the fact that many researchers have tried a variety of methods with little success. There is no denying steganography's importance and importance in the field of cryptic and secure data transmission. Information security has improved significantly using a combination of steganography and other techniques, such as cryptography(Nabi & Afzal, 2020).

1.3 Research Questions

RQ 1: How can we improve the quality of the stego-image?

RQ 2: Is it possible to make the stego-image more secure?

1.4 Objective

This research paper investigates some novel ways to improve the perceptibility of steganography in digital images, as well as the security of secret messages, and how steganography algorithms can be better applied in the field of data security to ensure information sharing veracity. The goal of this project are:

1. To create a system and validate an approach that will provide performance improvements over the steganography methods suggested in previous research. To achieve this goal, I present an integrated LSB steganographic approach in which the image's least significant bit is replaced with a data bit to improve the quality of stego medium. This is in line with the trend of improving image imperceptibility
2. To improve security of the stego-image(payload). I used the AES algorithm, which employs a symmetric key encryption technique.

1.5 Contributions

The security and integrity of LSB technique on secrete message can be further enhanced upon the application of the following points:

1. Able to determine that LSB technique can be used to improve payload imperceptibility (stego-image).
2. I also confirmed that the AES algorithm is suitable for data security or privacy protection by launching a brute force attack. I compared the locally built tool (solution) with another web application open source tool called(Steganographic Encoder).

1.6 Motivation

In this emerging era of accelerated change of overwhelming complexity and tremendous competition with the ever increase of malicious attacks, adversaries of different types continue to pose a challenge on private sector and government documents in the cyber world which has motivated information technology analysts and developers to pursue technological solutions to protect the privacy of information transmitted over communication networks(Rashid et al., 2017). The study is inspired by the the following: Firstly, problems that the field of security faces. secondly, the desire to find a very promising solution, exploit the advantages and influence of steganography to this day. Thirdly, To emphasize more secure solutions for protecting confidential data that are being transmitted over communication channels, and to improve the payload quality, and to increase the integrity of the payload.

Over the last few decades, steganographic information security systems have been a significant focus of research. Researchers normally attempt to overcome a trade-off between hiding capacity and stego quality. Large quantities of data hidden in the cover medium usually degrades the quality of the

stego medium, and vice versa. As a result, hiding capacities have remained relatively low due to this adverse effect on quality(Rabie et al., 2018).

In addition, one of the goals of implementing the Steganography approach is to avoid drawing attention or dissuade suspicion towards the transmission of hidden information which strict confidentiality is required. If suspicion is aroused, this aim, which was devised to ensure the security of secret messages, will be pursued, due to the hacker(s) may have noticed some changes in the sent post, this observer will try to deduce the secret information hidden inside the image.

1.7 Thesis organization

This thesis comprises of four(4) chapters and the organization context of this thesis entails the following:

- I. The first chapter covers an overview of steganography, as well as the issue statement, research questions, goals, contribution, and motivation.
- II. The second chapter provides an introduction to steganography, including types of steganography, steganography methods, and related research.
- III. The proposed work and methodology are presented in Chapter 3, as well as design factors for the suggested model, the hidden file data layout, cover file data layout, and the algorithm for embedding and extracting the data.
- IV. Execution of the suggested model, empirical work, and discussion of findings are accorded in Chapter 4.
- V. Last but not least, conclusions and future work are addressed in Chapter 5.

Chapter 2

RELATED WORK

2. Related work

This section presents some of the LSB-based image steganography techniques that have been tested and proven by other researchers using various steganography domains. (Padmavathi & Kumari, 2013) studied various encryption techniques like AES, DES and RSA algorithms along with LSB substitution techniques. Agreeing to that, (Cem et al., 2018) stated that “the aim of steganography is to conceal the details transmitted via a communication channel”, thereby making the existence of hidden messages goes unnoticed. Steganography has concentrated on numerous strategies for improving the concealment of hidden details in cover media (Rashid et al., 2017). However, it posed an interesting argument here in that it did not take into account the credibility issues that might arise if the cover media were changed by an attacker (Rashid et al., 2017). It is more important to ensure the safety of your data than to hide it (Faleh, 2014). On the other hand, (Nabi & Afzal, 2020) carried out a study on picture steganography, as well as various other techniques and sub-techniques Which includes a selection of a recent pattern ROI (Region Of Interest) and performance indicators that were derived from different types of image file used in the image steganography.

An improvement was suggested Cem et al. (2018) by recommending the use of a CRC-32 checksum, The secret message is then compressed with Gzip before being it is encrypted with AES, and it is evenly merged to an encrypted header information for processing before being inserted into the carrier image. Mr. Cem's results demonstrated that LSB together with AES was able to overcome LSB's flaws. The paper by (Jassim, 2013), noted that researchers have reported different techniques but all the methods suffer with image quality problems, the author added that most data hiding systems take advantage of human perceptual weaknesses. Steganography, in the view of (Mr. Jassim), is often confused with cryptography since the two are used to secure sensitive knowledge in similar ways. Establishing a secure channel for exchanging information with others is known to be one of the major problems which is not only applicable to this century but throughout history, says Mr. Jassim. A study by (Riasat et al., 2011) observed that the available approaches, typically used for colour image steganography, uses various symmetric-key cryptographic algorithms such as AES, DES, and IDEA but some of these algorithms are very slow and not good for bulky sized data. (Riasat et al.) went on to prove that a variety of algorithms, including Message Digest 5 (MD5), Bit Stream Ciphers (BSC), Stable Hash Algorithm (SHA), and others, are based on cryptographic hash functions that use a 16-byte hash key. However, due to inherent shortcomings in the used checksum technique, these algorithms are vulnerable in terms of providing protection.

The capacity of steganographic information security systems has been a major area of research over the past couple of decades ie et al., 2018). The relationship between the hiding capacity and stego quality is typically characterized by a trade-off that researchers try to overcome. The quality of the stego medium is usually lowered when vast volumes of data are hidden in the cover medium, and vice versa. As a consequence of this negative impact on efficiency, hiding capacities have remained comparatively poor (Rabie et al.). The steganographic limit and indistinctness are the two basic angles in steganographic technique. Whatever the case may be, these two characteristics are incompatible with

one another. Furthermore, it is extremely difficult to extend the steganographic cap while maintaining the technique's imperceptibility. Furthermore, there are only very few steganography methods that can be used for correspondence conventions, which speak to a whimsical yet motivating steganography medium. Consequently, this exploration addresses and proposes a few techniques to improve these major parts of digital photo steganography (Kalia et al., 2019). When it comes to security, “the best method is DWT which offers high degree of robustness while LSB offer no security but more payload embedding capability with less complexity” says (Nabi & Afzal, 2020). Due to high robustness, low ease of detection and good payload capacity is very good for steganography. Distortion methods carry less distortion in stego-image. Gray level approach provides strong payload with low complexity for an 8-bit image. The capability vs. security trade-off is a big factor when embedding a code. Both have been discovered to be reciprocal to one another. When protection is strengthened or expanded, capability is decreased. This calls for the need of a steganographic technique capable of optimizing performance metric under different (Nabi & Afzal, 2020). With the advancement in technology, data security or data privacy has become increasingly important as more and sophisticated systems connected to the internet. Following that, in order to ensure the security or safety of information transmission via any communication channel has become an important research issue. And to guarantee security of information during transmission, there are two ways to solve this problem. One approach is through cryptography and the other is steganography (Emam et al., 2016).

A comparison by (Padmavathi & Kumar, 2013) between three different encryption algorithms for data encryption and then the encrypted file is hidden within an image by using LSB substitution technique. Based on the outcome of the experiments, it was determined that the AES algorithm consumes the least amount of encryption and decryption time and buffer use as compared to the DES algorithm, but the RSA algorithm absorbs more encryption time and has a very high buffer use. Also observed that decryption of AES algorithms is better than other algorithms. From the simulation result, they evaluated that the AES algorithm is much better than the DES and RSA algorithm, which makes it more efficient when applied in the enhancement process of data security. Agreeably, (Riasat et al., 2011) added that the available methods, which are widely used for color image steganography, use various symmetric-key cryptographic algorithms such as AES, DES, and IDEA, but these algorithms are sluggish and unsuitable for large volumes of data. Other algorithms, such as BSC, MD5, and SHA, are inefficient when it comes to providing flawless security. Because of these issues with existing methods, the field of steganography has remained unpopular and unsuccessful. There is no questioning steganography's popularity and importance in the field of cryptic and secure data transfer over the internet, but there is a need for a stronger and improved algorithm that is not only effective but also secure. The power of digital images is estimated in bits per pixel, according to (Rabie et al., 2018). (bpp). For the last two decades, researchers have focused on the potential of steganographic information protection programs. And as a result, hiding large amounts of data into the cover medium decreases the quality of the stego medium and vice versa. As a result, hiding capacities have remained relatively low due to this adverse effect on quality. Mr. Rabie also propounded that recent work has tried to overcome the stego quality-capacity barrier in images by using the Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT). The

Discrete Cosine Transform is a method for converting a signal from one domain to another. Due to its powerful "energy compaction" property, DCT is a common transform in signal and image processing applications.

A model was introduced in the MATLAB R2015a framework in a paper by (Rashid et al., 2017). Explained that because of the appropriate file checksum, the R2015a version was chosen. The experimental work made use of uncompressed grayscale photographs as PGM format cover artifacts. The deployed scheme employed the LSB(least significant bits) method that uses 4 LSB bits to conceal the payload and also for the verification of integrity of decoy data. Anwar et al. (2019) suggested the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) - Base64 as a way to secure messages and different file formats stored in digital images. Until being encoded into the picture using the LSB process, secret messages are encrypted using the AES and Base64 techniques. The analysis indicated a combination of LSB-AES-Base64 algorithms on various files and the size of the cover image for measurement of imperceptibility performance work. The stego image histogram is also identical to the original image says (Anwar et al., 2019). The paper by (Prabhakar et al., 2018) describes the concept behind AES. Advance encryption standard(AES) algorithm was applied in order to achieve a higher degree of security mainly used for encryption before it is been inserted into the cover image, while the LSB method was employed for the concealing of the secret message. Although, (Molato et al., 2018) suggested that using the Huffman encoding along with the theory of quadratic residues added an extra layer of robustness, meanwhile the embedding process is directly done in the YCbCr color space rather than the original RGB color space of the cover picture.

2.1 History of Steganography

Steganography is the art of transmitting data in a format that conceals the fact that it is being sent. The name steganography is derived from the Greek terms $\sigma\tau\epsilon\gamma\alpha\nu\acute{o}\varsigma$ (steganos), which means "covered, veiled, or secured," and $\gamma\rho\acute{\alpha}\phi\epsilon\iota\nu$ (graphein), which means "writing." On the other hand, cryptography conceals the contents of a secret message, steganography conceals the very fact that a message is communicated i.e. steganography does conceal the very information used as evidence. The concept of steganography was first introduced in 1499, but the idea itself has existed since ancient times.

According to legend, during the Roman Empire, a slave selected to deliver a hidden message had his scalp shaved clean and a message tattooed into his skin. The messenger was sent on his quest after his hair grew back. The letter was read after the recipient shaved the messenger's head once more. Throughout the 20th century, steganography and steganalysis (the practice of assessing whether or not hidden information is being transmitted inside a carrier) were actively developed. There are many security methodology, techniques and technology that many come to terms with data protection but in our case the most considered of these techniques are Steganography and Cryptography. Steganography, also known as "covered writing," is extracted from two Greek words "stegos" signifying "cover" and "grafia" meaning "writing." Only images are hidden in picture steganography, masking the fact that data is being submitted. In Herodotus' Histories, the first instance of steganography can be identified.

This ancient practice originated from Greece during the Ionian Revolt. Histiaeus, who happens to be the ruler of Miletus was abroad but he needed to communicate with his son-in-law, Aristagoras, in order to plan for his return and this is where steganography falls into picture. He shaved the head of one of the most trusted slaves and tattooed the message on the scalp of the slave and afterwards waited for the slave's hair to grow back and before being shipped with the hidden message with a clear instruction to shave the slave's hair. When the message reaches Aristagoras, he performs the reverse of the process used in hiding the message i.e. shave the messenger's scalp in order to read the message.

Another story was told by Herodotus on steganography that took place several years during the reign of the Spartan king Demaratus who sent a blank waxed tablet to Sparta. Embedded in this blank waxed tablet was a message to warn the Spartans of Xerxes' invasion plan. These were some of the earlier records of steganography. Thereafter, a more sophisticated embodiment of steganography was recorded in the 4th century BC. Another technique called the hole punching technique was mentioned by Aeneas Tacticus. The idea of invisible inks, writing was first discussed by Philo of Byzantium in the third century BC. Gall nuts were used to write the letter, and a copper sulfate solution was used to expose it in his approach. Steganography is a concept that comes from Johannes Trithemius' book *Steganographia*. Steganography is a mixture of the Greek words "steganos" (hidden) and "graphein" (writing). Thereafter, Polygraphia was adopted, and later published after the death of Trithemius' in 1518. This book enlightens more about steganography and its practice.

Furthermore, Francis Bacon came up with Bacon's cipher in 1605. This approach involved encoding a hidden message into a seemingly harmless text using two separate typefaces. Then came Microdots, which were invented in the nineteenth century but had no influence in the field of steganography. Later, the use of letter or picture to the size of a dot, was introduced during World War I. Which allows people to connect and exchange data in an unnoticed manner. This is known as steganography, which is the optical equivalent of invisible ink. It's like digging for a needle in a haystack to locate the secret info. The method makes it possible for hackers to deliver data-stealing malware invisibly. That doesn't mean that people can't discover steganographic attacks. This is as a result that these defense techniques, on the other hand, inscribe other aspects of the attacks, not the steganography challenges itself. Unlike Cryptography, which deals with the transformation, encryption or conversion of plaintext into ciphertext or unreadable format. Steganography focuses on burying or concealing the existence of information, while cryptography is more apprehensive with ensuring that the information is not accessible. By its very nature, when steganography is executed correctly, not a soul – with the exception of the intended recipient should be capable to identify that there is any disguised communication in progress. This makes it more suitable in situations where obvious information is unsafe.

2.2 Basic terms in Image steganography

In this paper, some of the following definitions or terms are used includes:

- Payload: The word payload refers to the information that will be hidden and delivered anonymously, or the data that will be transmitted covertly;
- Carrier (stego-container): Any object in which the payload is secretly inserted is referred to as a carrier (stego-container or cover image);
- Stego-system: The methods and means employed in the development of a hidden medium for the transmission of information;
- Channel: The carrier is moved through a data transmission channel;
- Key: The key that is used to embed and extract the payload (into and out) of the carrier.

2.3 Steganography Techniques

There are several strategies available, each with its own set of benefits and drawbacks. (Kaur & Behal, 2014) looked at various types of steganography techniques. These steganographic methods and algorithms have been developed and validated scientifically. They are as follows: Least significant Bit(LSB), Direct Cosine Transform (DCT), and Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) which are all security-enhancing techniques.

2.3.1 Spatial domain

A number of steganographic methods and algorithms have been developed and validated scientifically. A simple explanation for the spatial domain, and under this category the least significant bits (LSB) belong. It basically operates by replacing the bits from the payload(Rashid et al., 2017). Spatial domain methods specifically embed signals in the strength of pixels (Morkel et al., 2005). Although each domain has its own strengths and weaknesses, “image steganography in the spatial domain is much preferable in terms of simplicity, low computational complexity and high payload capacity” (Molato et al., 2018). The easiest technique is spatial technique, also known as substitution technique, which deals with modifying an image's bit pattern. In the cover image, the pixel values are directly inserted (Nabi & Afzal, 2020). Pixels display images in the spatial domain; except the less important parts of the cover object are removed without changing the entire cover object. It is the most basic technique for data concealment, but it is extremely vulnerable to even simple attacks such as compression (Kaur & Behal, 2014). Including the fact that experts have critically examined the LSB technique's weakness. However, some of its benefits are: the distortion from original image during the embedding process of information is difficult to spot due to its high hiding capacity. (Nabi & Afzal, 2020) added that there are primarily two types of images: 8-bit and 24-bit (RGB). The former has 256 colors, while the latter supports $256*256*256=$ approximately 16 million different colors. LSB usually deals with RGB images, with embedding that can be performed sequentially or randomly.

It's difficult to notice the subtle color variation. As a result, this approach takes advantage of the Human Visual System (HVS) inherent flaw. This technique can be applied to both grayscale and color images by altering any 8 bits of image data in the grayscale image so that the change is undetectable to the naked eye. In addition, when working with RGB images, the least important bit of each color variable should be used. As a result, the possible capacity for concealing hidden data in an RGB picture is three times that of a grayscale image of the same size (Rashid et al., 2017).

Fig 2.3.1(a) : Simple illustration of image steganography concept.

Fig 2.3.1(b). The basic concept of LSB embedding method.

Palette-based image steganography is a subtype of LSB steganography in which the communicated data is converted into the image palette's least important bits rather than the carrier's. The apparent disadvantage of this approach is its limited data storage space.

2.3.2 Transform domain

Transform domain embedding is a category of frequency domain embedding strategies in which an image is represented by its frequencies (Kaur & Behal, 2014). To conceal the sensitive data in the cover picture, frequency techniques including Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) & Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) are used (Raja et al., 2005).

1. Discrete Cosine Transform Technique (DCT): To transform image files from the spatial domain into the frequency domain, it would be required to apply the DCT mathematical equation. The payload is encoded inside least significant bits of the communication channel frequency components after the image has been transformed in frequency domain and is defined for lossy compression.

2. Discrete Wavelet Transform Technique (DWT): The Discrete Wavelet Transform Technique (DWT) is a technique that uses discrete wavelets to transform data. It's a statistical function for converting optical image data from the spatial to frequency domain.

2.4 COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT STEGANOGRAPHIC TECHNIQUES

Steganography Techniques	Cover Media	Embedding Techniques	Advantages
Image Hiding	Image		
1.LSB(Least Significant Bit)		The LSB(least significant bit) known to be the simplest technique for embedding of information within the pixel of an image and offers a high hiding capacity.	The simplest and most straightforward method of concealing information.
2.DCT (Discrete Cosine Transform)		By changing the transformed DCT coefficient, it embeds the details.	Hidden data can be spread more uniformly across the entire image, making it more stable.
3.DWT (Discrete Wavelet transform)		This method uses a large number of wavelets to encrypt an entire image.	Under a tolerable level of noise, the wavelet coefficient is altered.

Figure 2.4 Comparison of different steganographic techniques (Kaur & Behal, 2014) as explained in Figure 2.5

2.5 Categories of Steganographic Systems

Steganographic architectures can be divided into three types based on the embedding and extraction methods used (Mishra et al., 2014), they are as follows:

2.5.1 Simple steganography (or No Key Steganography - NKS): The payload is embedded inside a cover image without the use of a key in plain steganography, also known as "No Key steganography." This is the most fundamental and vulnerable kind of steganography. The success of this disguised communication is based on the perpetrators' unawareness that this cover contains a coded message.

2.5.2 Secret Key Steganography (SKS): In concealed or secret key steganography, the payload is encoded in the cover image and extracted from the stego image using the hidden key. The keys in this system of steganography are normally chosen by both the receiver and the transmitter. Prior to transmission, the keys used for concealing the information can be shared among the parties involved through a safe channel and this could be one of the most difficult aspect of this form of technique. Even though, It is very reliable in the protecting system confidentiality.

2.5.3 Public Key Steganography (PKS): In this method, it involves the use of two(2) pairs. i.e. a public and private keys to conceal classified information. In order to retrieve the sensitive information, the intended recipients needs to be aware of both keys used during the embedding process, and likewise the correct employed encryption algorithms. "As a consequence, this strategy is considered to be dependable" (Mishra et al., 2014).

2.6 Types of Steganography

Cover audio, video, and image will all be used for embedding, resulting in stego-audio, stego-video, and stego-image (Kaur & Behal, 2014). The basic prerequisite to begin image steganography is the selection of an image or cover image. The use of a suitable cover image and algorithm will improve the embedding rate and payload capability of the cover image. JPEG, GIF, BMP, PNG, TIFF, and JPEG 2000 are the most popular. Lossless images are favoured for data embedding (Nabi & Afzal, 2020). It can be said that almost any digital file format can be used for steganography purpose, but those with high redundancy are considered more suitable. Redundancy is characterized as the bits of an object that provide much greater precision than is required for the object's use and display. There are two kinds of image compression: lossy and lossless, and different steganographic algorithms have been created for both (Morkel et al., 2005). As illustrated in Figures 4.6(a) and 4.6(b).

Figure 2.6 : Types of Steganography

2.6.1 Text Steganography

Historically, the most effective technique of steganography has been to conceal detail in text. An easy solution would be to conceal a hidden message in the n th letter of every word of a text message. Text steganography with digital files is uncommon because text files contain very little redundant data. There are various strategies for concealing information in text. However, when it comes to sending large amount of data, they are not very efficient or useful due to the text files are usually very thin. An alternative is to type in the text into Microsoft Word, and later change the text color to white. And advise them about how to access the information through a safe channel. Otherwise, they might be perplexed as to why you keep giving them blank pages. This is not a very safe approach and someone who intercepts the communications would suspect you of transmitting blank documents all the time. All they have to do is click the text, and your scheme will be thwarted, - Lake, Josh (2019)

2.6.2 Image steganography

The most famous cover items used for steganography are pictures. Many distinct image file formats exist in the realm of digital files, the majority of which are designed for particular purposes. There are various steganographic algorithms for these various image file formats. “Most images on the Internet are represented as bits also known as rectangular map of the image's pixels, each pixel and what color it is” (Morkel et al., 2005). In image steganography, the larger the amount of hidden message inserted within a cover image, the more the cover image would be distorted. As a result, the success of an image steganography technique is largely determined by its undetectability, whether by visual inspection or statistical analysis (Molato et al., 2018).

2.6.3 Audio/Video steganography

Audio steganography is also available in a number of methods. As for all forms of steganography, it is vital that the methods are stable, capable of holding a sufficient amount of hidden information, Lake, Josh (2019). Among the most common strategies are:

- **Least significant bit coding** – Supports the modification of limit important sections of the audio data without affecting altering the sound.
- **Echo hiding** – This supports make an undercover of data in an echo.
- **Tone insertion** – Difficult to distinguish when they are close to those that are far more effective, these lower energy tones may be used to mask details.

2.7 Steganography VS Cryptography

Steganography by definition involves hiding the presence of a payload or secret, on the other hand cryptography focus on shielding or protecting the hidden information. “If steganography is properly applied, it almost impossible for the third party to spot any secret contact” - Lake, Josh (2019). As a result, it is an important method in situations where close contact is hazardous. Cryptography, on the other hand, is typically used where people are unconcerned whether someone finds out that they are exchanging information but want the message itself to be hidden and inaccessible to third parties. For instance, the arrangements can be difficult if you are a political leader who has been arrested and needs to connect with your organisation. Since the authorities will be able to trace anything that passes in and out of your mobile device, you will almost definitely have to mask all communication that occurs. In this case, steganography will be a safe alternative. Assume you're an ambassador communicating with your home country over classified information. “Diplomats are expected to speak with officials in their own government, but the communications must not raise any concern. And because the nature of the communication is classified, the diplomat would opt to speak over an encrypted line using cryptography”. Still on Lake, Josh (2019) blog post, in order to examine the difference, it is important to look at this instance from a different angle. Imagine a situation where a political activist uses cryptography to exchange among his group, it is likely that the message can be intercepted by the police and if found wanting that there has been an initiated session transmitting encrypted messages, they might either investigate it further or halt the transmission and question the activist about it. This could lead to beatings, torture, or even the death of the protester. As a result, steganography will be more fitting in this situation. Diplomats, on the other hand, are often supervised by their host countries. If a diplomat attempted to transmit steganographically concealed messages back home, the messages could be intercepted, interpreted, and the content revealed. In this scenario, encryption is preferable so interceptors will be aware that correspondence is taking place but will be unable to decide what it is about.

2.8 Combining steganography & cryptography

Cryptography and steganography are completely two different security strategies that can be used independently, or they can also be combined together to enhance security. You may choose to encrypt the payload or fact that you were communicating but still protecting it in case it was discovered. In such instance, you will need to conceal it with steganography. For example, you want to hide a message "I'm going home" through the user of a simple Caesar cipher algorithm and invisible ink - (Lake Josh, 2019). You can use the cipher to change every single character, to achieve a ciphertext like the one below:

J'n hpjoh ipnf

You can make use of lemon juice to write down this text into a sheet of paper. And the recipient may have known where to find the information as far as they are informed and knows where to look for, in order to uncover the message using (heat in this case), and how to decipher it. Someone who intercepts the letter but is unable to detect the invisible ink may be unaware that contact has occurred. If they detect the existence of a message but are unable to decrypt it, the message remains would remain protected, even though the intruder is aware that communicate is taking place until they are able to crack the code.

2.8.1 Criteria for Steganography

To assess the efficiency of steganographic techniques, three common criteria may be used: Security, capacity, and imperceptibility.

1. **Robustness:** The degree of complexity needed to destroy embedded data without damaging the cover image is referred to as robustness (C.P et al., 2013). According to the seminaronly blog post, steganography system may be exposed to a variety of either active form of attacks or even or passive attacks. Seemingly, these forms of attacks can be used to impede communication between users. Steganography can be called safe in the presence of such steganalytic schemes if the presence of payload's or hidden message can only be inferred with a frequency no greater than random guessing Otherwise, we might claim it's insecure.
2. **Capacity:** "This can be describe simply the most amount of information that can be concealed inside a cover image. It's measured in bits per pixel (bpp)",(Swain & Lenka, 2014). In order for steganography to be effectively useful when transmitting payloads of secrete message, it is necessary that hiding capacity provided by the system is of high quality. The size of the payload can be relatively or absolutely measured usually termed as embedding rate, bit per pixel or the ratio of the payload etc.
3. **Imperceptibility:** This is referred to as the resistance to both human visual system and statistical experiments which can be calculated using the peak signal noise ratio (PSNR). The Stego photographs that are obtained should be of high quality and free of extreme visual objects. The higher the fidelity of the stego picture, under the same degree of protection and power, the better. If the resulting stego image is harmless enough, one may assume that this condition has

been met, despite the warden's lack of the original cover image. When using steganography to conceal communication, imperceptibility becomes the most important requirement, although robustness and potential capacity could be sacrificed (Hamid et al., 2012). Figure 2.8.1 depicts a tradeoff between those properties:

Figure 2.8.1: Properties Tradeoff between Image Steganography (Hamid N. et al., 2012).

2.8.2 The uses of steganography

Aside from the simple one of covering data and texts, steganography has a host of surprising uses. It's used by hackers to hide coding in malware attacks. Printers, too, use steganography to hide inconspicuous yellow dots that reveal which printer made a text and when. To prove possession and copyright, watermarking and fingerprinting also make extensive use of steganographic techniques says Lake, Josh (2019).

2.8.3 The limitations of steganography

Steganography is considered to be a very useful method, although it has some downsides. Some of these factors which are often in conflict includes:

- a.) The first is how clear and simple it is to find secret data .i.e. whether through human intuition or through other methods of study - Lake, Josh (2019).
- b.) Secondly, what is the total volume of data that can be concealed within a cover file.

Attempting to hide huge volume or amount of payload, the easier it is to detect. steganographic technique is one of the determining factor in the volume of secret message can individual can adequately insert into a cover file. Other considerations include the degree of vulnerability and the expected level of scrutiny. After concealing of data is concealed in photos, the human eye also has a rough time detecting irregularities after 20% of the payload has been substituted, indicating that the information has been securely concealed. The picture would basically appear the same at lower percentages. When more data is crammed in, the consistency begins to deteriorate, and you can see hints of the secret picture. For instance, if about 20% is be used for concealing of payload, it is recommended that the file should be at least five times the size of the secrete message that is to be concealed. You'd need a

five-gigabyte file for each gigabyte you choose to hide for this strategy at a low risk level. As a consequence, steganography is unreliable. "If the aim is to keep data encrypted and confidential rather than disclosing that information exchange has been initiated, then in such case cryptography is normally a suitable option" - Lake, Josh (2019). In addition to the efficiency problem, the receiver must understand where and how knowledge has been hidden in order to gain access to it. This implies that the sender would need a more secure channel in order to exchange this information in order to avoid risk of being intercepted by an intruder. This can be a difficult problem to solve since reliable networks are always hard to acquire, especially in circumstances that involve steganography - Lake, Josh (2019). Finally, Mr. Lake added that it is important to keep Kerckhoff's theory in mind when attempting to conceal messages: "A cryptosystem ought to be safe even if the information concerning the scheme or architecture is open to the public, except the key." Also, it is not wise to set up a system that only security is the intruder's lack of knowledge or awareness to find it and compromise the secret and unlock the secret on how to retrieve the information. Therefore, in situations where the ultimate goal is to secure information from unauthorized access, then it is highly advised that the payload should be first encrypted using a private key before applying steganographic techniques.

2.8.4 Steganography detection

Steganography is often incredibly difficult to detect, especially when there's no reason to be suspicious. Within the cyber world, we always come across a lot of information or data that sometimes it is almost difficult for us to take the time to carefully examine every aspect which appears to be legitimate in our eyes before processing it further. This is an aspect that makes it difficult to discuss a superior or quality concept of steganography. Most of the already existing examples discussed have been acknowledged as failures and are now considered to be public information - Lake, Josh (2019). Concordantly, techniques are being extensively researched and developed, although a successful steganography in of itself is almost impossible to detect. Techniques formed outside of the generic authority domain, such as through intelligence forces, terrorism networks, and crime groups, may also spread. We won't know until we come across such kind of tools. Even so, a plethora of computational methods are often used when we assume that steganography is being utilized to conceal communications. On the other hand, the proper tool for identifying when steganography is being used depends on the kind of applied techniques for hiding the secret message.

2.8.5 physical steganography detection

In the case of invisible ink application, the means of disclosure are determined based on the type of ink used to conceal the message. For instance, if the process was incorrectly performed, this could possibly leave some marks on the paper (i.e. a difference in appearance), this might leave some leads or clues for intruders to easily spot the area where the information is being concealed. If suspicion is raised, this would motivate the intruder(s) to make more effort towards unlocking the secret behind the invisible ink. With the notion that the letter carries with it an invisible ink. The first step would be to check if

there are any visual disparity. The next step would be to find a way to extract the information to an ultraviolet light, which reveals various types of invisible ink. The message will then be disclosed to sun, revealing other types of ink. If you still haven't found the message, another option would be to make use of iodine fumes.

There might be situations that none of those methods function, in such case you are unable to manifest that a message is not hidden. It might be likely that adversary may also be using a complex invisible ink approach that you are completely ignorant of. Inconsistency behind text can also be identified through the use of null ciphers. Since the sender is attempting to generate their hidden message into the cover text, through the use of odd phrase. It can be said that, in case the null cipher is well-completed and you have no need to examine it closely, it is frequently possible for people to get hidden message without you knowing. Similarly, Bacon's ciphers are frequently identified while looking for inconsistencies. Intruders can look at fonts, spacing, sizing, and a variety of other considerations in suspect document. Again, if handled well, it is always difficult to prove if a hidden message is present. It is also said that microdots are almost impossible to detect due to their limited scale, except if the intruder is still suspicious - Lake, Josh (2019).

2.8.6 Digital steganography detection

Considering that digital steganography can be very hard to spot. As a result, it is unlikely to investigate one's records in every significant manner, except if you are skeptical or the cryptosystem was mishandled. In case steganographic application is found on one's computer, or whether they have a record for browsing steganography-related websites, this could serve as important hints - Lake, Josh (2019). This can be straightforward hint denoting that the suspect may have put to use steganography to conceal information, and might even have hints on how must they applied it. After retrieving the first version of the file, then it would be easier to detect the steganographic modifications. All you need do is simply to match the hashing of the cover file to the hashing of the stego file. In case the hashing do not match, then it means that the file has been altered and does contains secret info Lake, Josh (2019). In case the above technique is not feasible, steganography could also be identified using statistical analysis. Although the human eyes and ears cannot discern coded material in images and audio, the main evidence can also be readily identified when looking for statistical irregularities. Identifying steganography is just one component of the process. Even if steganography is discovered and the prosecutor is almost confident that it holds secret messages, they would not be able to discover it. Assuming the investigators lacks the necessary steganographic resources, then it is likely that they may will not be able to decode or hack the algorithm. Even of steganography is discovered by an intruder, does not mean failure for the communicators. It all comes down to their initial intent for sending the message. If the utmost aim is that information exchange remains on stealth mode, by discovering the application of steganography, it would jeopardise their strategy. On other hand, , both parties can be securely rest assured only if the interceptor cannot gain entry to information.

2.8.7 Why is steganography becoming more popular?

So, why is it that malware writers are increasingly using steganography in their work? We believe there are three major explanations for this:

- It allows them to hide not only the data but also the fact that it is being uploaded and downloaded.
- It aids in the circumvention(bypassing) of DPI schemes, which is essential for corporate systems.

Since anti-APT software can't process all image files, steganography may be used to get around security checks (corporate networks contain too many of them, and the analysis algorithms are rather expensive). To capture suspects, computer forensics researchers have long used advanced techniques of intercepting encrypted files and combining them for metadata to decide who is communicating with whom, where, and for how long. Law enforcement and technology experts pay particular attention to this form of encryption. According to the IEEE.org publication, criminals, on the other hand, are becoming more sophisticated. Criminals and radicals are now conversant with the rise in attention towards encryption and are constantly seeking for new strategies and tools to keep their malicious activities hidden by using steganographic software, which is largely in the aspect of smuggling stolen data (in situation that it is most necessary to avoid prompting (IDS & IPS) intrusion detection/ prevention systems). The most current and important pattern is a devised means to arm malware with data wrapping capabilities, or techniques that mask information says the IEEE.org publication.

2.9 Quality Evaluation Metric

Two known metrics PSNR and MSE are mainly used to access the quality of an image. PSNR stands for Peak Signal to Noise Ratio and MSE stands for Mean Square Error. PSNR is typical used to calculate the proportion between maximum potential power of sign and power of corrupting distortion that influences the image accuracy. Mainly, the ratio is used to differentiate between the quality of a stego image containing hidden data to that of an empty cover image. On the other hand, MSE is simply the average squared disparity between a cover image and a stego image. A lower MSE value means less variations between both images, resulting in a higher PSNR. Steganography usually offered great deal of help, although it must be used in the best circumstances – where you wish to conceal the fact that information exchange is taking place. If used correctly, you'll be able to deliver hidden messages without an intruder even knowing it - Lake, Josh (2019). However, steganography is considered completely useless in some situations. In a situation where it doesn't matter whether an intruder notice that you are exchanging information, but it is expected that the details of the correspondence must stay private, cryptography can be used instead. Which in turn makes steganography of less importance here. However, if stealthy mode is the desired goal for establishing a communication session in the first place, then steganography would best serve the purpose. Mr. Lake clarified that encryption is consider to be more easier and that even more data is

often encrypted inside the same volume. You can also connect without a safe channel using methods like public-key encryption. When steganography used alone, it provides protection by anonymity, which can result in the breach of data. It is very important to apply steganography and cryptography in a situation where we expect absolute secrecy, .i.e. without the intruder knowing the content of the communication, So that eventually should the data get intercepted during transmission. This combination supplies more complex security. the advantages of both strategies and can shield you and your data from vulnerability.

Chapter 3

METHODOLOGY

3.1 An Overview of the proposed methodology

The employed methodology for this study focuses on practical or experimental work for embedding or inserting sensitive data or information into a canopy image using the LSB process, and using AES (Advanced Encryption Standard) for encryption of the embedded data into the stego image for security proof measure, a dictionary attack was launched against the resulting stego image. The aim of the attack is to verify/validate the protection level as well as to find any bugs or flaws. Python is the programming language used to execute the proposed model. Embedding is the method of encoding the hidden message in a cover image, which is then stored as a stream of bytes. Extract-Verify: is concerned with both the extraction of the hidden message and the verification of the derived secret's message credibility. (Gyamfi et al., 2017) suggested a high-volume information concealment technique focused on the combination of Cryptography and Steganography. The information (message) is encrypted first using a 256 bit Key Length AES Algorithm, and the output result (encrypted message) is hidden inside an image using LSB insertion methodology. Using these two strategies offers more and better protection to the hidden content, as well as meeting criteria such as security, power, and robustness for safer and stable information transmission over an exposed channel.

Figure 3.1: Reading Secret Image as a Stream of Bytes(Rashid et al., 2017).

3.2 The main functional aspects Of the Proposed Method

The proposed work aims to improve the image imperceptibility and protection of a payload or hidden message that would be transmitted over communication networks by integrating the following:

1. To prevent an intruder from launching an attack, the main message is concealed inside an RGB or grayscale image sent over the channel. If the existence of a payload or hidden message is identified by a steganalysis software, and the intruder attempts to reveal the secret message.
2. It is expected that during the process of embedding a secret message, the generated stego image must be imperceptible i.e. with less likelihood of been detected.
3. The encryption process functions by translating readable text(plain text) into non-readable text also refer to as cipher text, which is composed of apparently random letters. AES operates based on symmetric key encryption, which entails using only one private key to encode and decode data.
4. Testing the (AES) encryption algorithm with bruteforce attack against the stego-system to make sure security of the key message. The Rijndael family of symmetric block cipher algorithms may be a subset

of AES, which is a variation of the names of two Belgian cryptographers, Joan Daemen and Vincent Rijmen. Wireless authentication, processor security, file encryption, and SSL/TLS are all examples of where AES encryption is used. In reality, AES was most likely used by your web browser to encrypt your access to this website. AES has proven to be very reliable and powerful, and when used with the correct key, it adds little to no overhead to any operation where it is used. AES is an easy and highly secure method of encryption that is commonly used by companies and governments around the world. AES is extremely stable, with a 256-bit encryption key that is almost unbreakable. While it would not take an eternity to break an AES 256-bit encryption key using advanced computer technologies, it would take much longer than all of our lifetimes. This is a brute-force approach, in which we try any combination before we hear the "click"/unlocking sound.

5. Verifying/comparison of stego-image against cover picture consistency.

6. Perform a reverse action on the stego image, to retrieve the hidden message.

3.3 Proposed Model Design Considerations

1. The hidden multimedia file will be read as a stream of bytes during the embedding process, regardless of its format.

2. A grayscale cover shot with a hidden multimedia file inserted in it.

3. By comparing the cover and stego images, the PSNR results should be similar to those obtained using normal image matching tools such as dCode.

3.4 The Secret File Data Layout

A stream of bytes is used to process the hidden multimedia file that will be inserted in the cover graphic. Figure 3.1 depicts the situation.

3.5 The Cover (Stego) File Data Layout

Every pixel in the RGB or grayscale cover image is made up of one byte (8 bits), with the embedded data stored in the right half-byte (4 bits) of each byte.

3.6 The Technique for processing

3.6.1 Algorithm for embedding

Regardless of the file type format, the payload will be interpreted one byte at a time. Combinations of steganography and cryptography techniques are also considered useful approaches for ensuring data protection and improving identity security, thanks to the latest internet trend.

Figure 3.6.1 Algorithm for Embedding

3.6.2 Algorithm for Extraction

The bytes of the stego file will be processed in sequence, beginning with the original hiding place. Each set of four bits derived from stego picture bytes will be combined to form a single hidden byte. The extraction will be carried out according to the following algorithms:

Figure 3.6.2: Algorithm for Extraction

Chapter 4

Experimental Results And Conclusion

4.1 Discussion of Experiment Results

4.1.1 Overview

The proposed steganography tool was created in the Python 3 context, and the encryption algorithm used was AES, which offers a high level of security. The applied scheme used the least significant bits (LSB) substitution technique to cover the payload or secret data.

Fig 4.1.1 (a) Splash screen

Fig 4.1.1(b) Operation interface

East-tec Invisible Secrets is an example of a steganography technique that I have used in the past. east-technology Invisible Secrets is a file encryption program that helps you keep your confidential records secure from prying eyes and unwanted access. This tool's trial version, on the other hand, has a limited set of tools. To access advanced features, users must subscribe to a premium version.

4.2 Metric for Evaluation

The following criteria are used to assess the proposed model's performance:

4.2.1 PSNR: When a stego image is relative to a duvet image, the PSNR (Peak signal noise ratio) value provides a measure of distortion. I used a web-based comparison of compression specifications for this. Standards for compression are compared online. This tool compresses and decompresses an image that has been imported by the user using different compression principles introduced by our IP cores. To assess their actual efficiency and explore the advantages each has to offer, the Bit Accurate Models of the respective image compression cores are used to encode / decode a user supplied test image. The decompressed files, as well as the achieved compression ratio, PSNR, and Structural Similarity (SSIM) parameters, are returned for visual inspection, and the compression efficiency of each image compression algorithm can be compared using the URL: (<https://www.alma-technologies.com/page.CompressionComparison>).

4.2.2 Security: During the process of brute force attack. The stego image created with the proposed tool was subjected to a dictionary attack using a tool called StegCracker. I reported that the StegCracker Tool was unable to decrypt the AES algorithm used on the steganographic tool's protection level. On the other hand, I successfully carried out the same brute force attack on an open source network steganographic method (Steganographic Encoder) using the URL: (<https://futureboy.us/stegano/encinput.html>). During the tests, it is used to assess the detection results. As cover pieces, the experimental work used uncompressed RGB photographs.

4.3 Sample Experiment

I used an image histogram method to measure the grayscale of an image to compare the produced stego image from the proposed model. An histogram is a schematic representation of the color spectrum in a numeric image's pixels. (<https://www.dcode.fr/image-histogram>) is the URL for the image histogram. Figures 4.7(a) and 4.7(b) demonstrate this.

4.4 Comparison of PSNR Results

A payload or hidden message was encoded in the RGB picture in this experiment. Two file formats were used to verify the embedding operation (PNG & JPG). For the end user, detecting a payload within a carrier may be a difficult task. Take a look at the two photos below as an example. The first is a payload carrier, and the second is a null carrier.

Figure 4.4 (a): Clean cover Image(Abraham.png)

Figure 4.4(b) Clean image(Abraham.jpg)

Figure 4.4 (c): Steo-Image(Abraham.png)

Figure 4.4(d) Steo-Image(Abraham.jpg)

4.5 TYPES OF IMAGE FILES

Photo steganography is largely dependent on the type of image used as the cover image, and each type embeds the hidden data in a particular way. “Some picture formats have a signature, although others don’t. JPEG, GIF, BMP, PNG, TIFF, and JPEG 2000 are the most popular. Images that are lossless are preferred” (Nabi & Afzal, 2020).

4.5.1 JPEG

JPEG expanded as Joint Photographic Experts Group abbreviated is a common web-friendly image format that supports approximately 16 million rich colors ¹. However, this is inefficient since a lot of detail is lost during image steganography. JPEG has a tendency to produce artifacts after compression. Despite these drawbacks, lossy compression is beneficial because it discards material that is undetectable to the naked eye and saves storage space. JPEG was formerly thought to be unsuitable for steganography due to its lossy appearance, but F5, Outguess, JSteg/JPHide, and others are all built on the JPEG format and have decent hiding. For the transformation of JPEG, DCT is used.

4.5.2 GIF

GIFs stands for Graphics Interchange Format are lossless images with an 8-bit color palette. It combines redundancy and various occurrence patterns into a single pattern, the GIF image files possess the attribute that supports the retrieval of the actual image from the generated compressed image.

4.5.3 BMP

Another image file type is bitmap image file commonly abbreviated as BMP. This image file format are substantial and the uncompressed version of the image support immense payload capacity that requires solid image steganography techniques. Although, it is not ideal to make use of BMPs as cover image to conceal mini data.

4.5.4 PNG

PNG files also known as Portable Graphics Format are the next generation of JPEG, but they are superior to JPEG in that they are lossless. The picture can be restored from a stego image due to its lossless nature. It doesn't support animation and only supports RGB, indexed colors, and gray-scale. influence and harm such as, The spatial method is useful for embedding capacity, but it is insecure.

4.5.5 JPEG2000 / JPEG2K

JPEG(Joint Photographic Experts Group) and JPEG2K files have gotten a lot of attention. JPEG's biggest weakness was its lossy design, which JPEG2K successfully overcomes.

4.6 Four (4) images PSNR values

Cover image(clean image)	Abraham.png (db)	Abraham.jpg(2000) (db)
Lossy grayscale PSNR	50.84	52.52
Lossy RBG PSNR	50.22	49.58
SSIM 1 grayscale	299.6	419.5
SSIM 1 RBG	451.0	397.5
Lossless compression ratio(Grayscale)	2.80: 1	3.18 : 1
Lossless compression ratio(RGB)	2.72 : 1	3.08 : 1

Figure 4.6(a) Clean cover image

Stego image	Abrahamstego.png (db)	Abraham-stego.jpg (db)
PSNR grayscale embedding	50.86	52.90
PSNR RGB embedding	50.24	50.13
SSIM 2 grayscale	299.6	469.4
SSIM 2 RGB	450.9	439.5
Lossless compression ratio(RGB)	2.72 : 1	3.16: 1
Lossless compression ratio(Grayscale)	2.80 : 1	3.34: 1

Figure 4.6(b) Stego images with payload(secret message)

4.7 PSNR FINDINGS

The photos on Figure 4.4 (a) and Figure 4.4 (b) were subjected to the PSNR (Peak signal noise ratio) evaluation described below:

Figure 4.7(a)

Figure 4.7(b)

Figure 4.7(a) shows a histogram representation of color distribution in grayscale (Abrahamstego.png), while Figure 4.7(b) shows a histogram representation of color distribution in grayscale (Abrahamstego.png) (Abraham-stego.jpg). Lossless compression, as previously said, refers to image compression that reduces the size of an image without sacrificing content.. This is usually accomplished by deleting old metadata from JPEG and PNG files.

The validation of my theorem (Q1) based on the PSNR lossless compression ratio (RGB) metric is based on realistic work. PSNR is used to estimate image quality after compression. The obtained PSNR lossless compression ration(RGB) can be deduced as follows: When the PSNR value is high, the image quality is highest. When the PSNR value is negative, the picture quality is considered to be bad.

On the opposite hand, to validate my hypothesis(Q2), I compared the locally built tool for my project against an open source tool called(Steganographic Encoder) by launching a brute force attack using Stegcracker tool kit. There was no success while attempting to retrieve the key from the stego-image that was generated through the tool locally built for my project. However, in an effort to retrieve a key from the stego-image that was achieved through the open source tool(Steganographic Encoder), the result was successful.

CONCLUSION

Centered on the achieved results from the proposed method. The techniques proves to be reliable when concealing secret message without sacrificing its security as a trade-off. LSB Image Steganography technique was employed for concealing the payload within a carrier image. In order to enhance security of the stego-system, the 256bit cryptography algorithm was used for encoding payload. Thereby, restricting intruders or unauthorised users access. After concealing the information inside a carrier(cover image), the newly generated image file is called stego image. Notably, researchers have proven via the data encryption algorithm - white paper that AES cryptography is considerably very reliable in terms security veracity, and as such makes it almost impossible for intruders to hack into the hidden information. In essence, the interception of the carrier(cover file) does not negates the potential of the AES. In addition, the application of LSB techniques shows its significance when concealing secret message within a stego image. Due to the amplitude that comes handy with this form of technique, it makes it extremely difficult for the human eye to recognise any noticeable changes in the stego .i.e. imperceptible to the human eyes). In the nutshell, both techniques empirically satisfied the goals of this paper.

FUTURE WORK

Based on the presented work of this research paper, future enhancement would focus on the following:

1. Apply a self-destructive flag into the stego image. i.e the stego-image will self-corrupt whenever an unauthorized attempt to decode the secret message(payload) is detected.
2. Verifying the stego's legitimacy by adding an integrity check flag to the payload or hidden data during the generation process. So that any interception or modification of the hidden message as it is being transmitted between the sender and the recipient may be detected.

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